

Impact on Electromechanical Oscillations of Grid-Forming VSGs: Spanish Grid Code

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Abstract—The advent of converter-interfaced generation (CIG) has brought about a significant shift in the landscape of power systems, giving rise to novel challenges that require careful consideration. One of the most significant issues that will need to be addressed in the future power system is the reduction of system inertia and damping. As a result, transmission system operators (TSOs) around the world are beginning to consider the impact of CIG on the power system in their grid codes. This work examines the impact of renewable energy sources on electromechanical oscillations, adopting the approach proposed by the Red Eléctrica de España (REE), the Spanish TSO. To this end, time-domain simulations are used to evaluate the effect of three types of grid-forming virtual synchronous generators on the damping and frequency of classical electromechanical oscillations.

Index Terms—Grid-forming, electromechanical power oscillation, inter-area oscillation, converter-interfaced generation, grid code.

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition to a power system dominated by renewable energy sources (RES) is now an undeniable fact. On the one hand, this is leading to a reduction in the carbon intensity of the sector as well as a reduction in the energy dependence of countries. On the other hand, the integration of these energy sources represents a significant challenge to the power system, primarily due to the replacement of synchronous generators by converter-interfaced generation (CIG). The considerable penetration of RESs is resulting in a notable reduction in the inertia and damping of the system increasing the frequency deviations [1] and power oscillations [2]. As a consequence, this is compromising the reliable and secure operation of the system, as well as its resilience to faults and contingencies [3]. An illustrative example of the consequences of the inertia reduction was the loss of a 2 GW transmission line between Spain and France due to a forest fire in the Pyrenees on 24th July 2021 [4]. This resulted in a frequency drop to 48.66 Hz when the RES share was about 34% jeopardizing the security and stability of the Spanish power system.

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With regard to power fluctuations, these are usually divided into low-frequency oscillations and sub-/super-synchronous oscillations [5]. The former are caused by electromechanical oscillations of low frequency between synchronous generators. On the contrary, sub-/super-synchronous oscillations have a wide range of oscillation frequencies [5].

In systems with high RES penetration, the CIGs contribute both to the classic low-frequency oscillations [6] and to the appearance of new oscillation modes [7]. They are mainly originated from the dynamic interaction between the controllers of different CIGs [8] or the CIGs controller and weak grids [9]. Examples of such oscillations have been documented in Xinjiang (China) between converter-based wind generators [10], which caused the trip of a large power plant and a HVDC. A further example of electromechanical oscillations was recorded in the European power system by ENTSO-E in 2016, when an underdamped 0.15 Hz oscillation occurred [11].

The origin of these oscillations and their damping is still an open question and a major concern in the operation of power systems. In fact, transmission system operators (TSOs) are beginning to include the study of this type of oscillations in their RES connection grid codes. Recently, the Spanish TSO has prepared a guide for the implementation of power oscillating damping (POD) controllers for wind and photovoltaic power plants, energy storage systems, hybrid facilities, FACTS and HVDC systems [12]. This guide is based on the Spanish Compliance Monitoring Technical Standard (NTS) [13], which specifies the methodologies to be used to evaluate the inter-area oscillations when integrating RESs, and the acceptable technical limits to authorise their integration into the Spanish power system.

In accordance with the proposed methodology for the connection of RES in the Spanish transmission system, this work presents a first exploration of the impact of grid-forming (GFM) virtual synchronous generators (VSGs) on electromechanical oscillations. To this end, three different types of GFM controllers are evaluated: (i) GFM based on a virtual synchronous generator [14], called S-VSG, (ii) GFM based on a synchroverter [15], called PI-VSG, and (ii) GFM based

on a synchronverter endowed with primary frequency response (PFR), through time-domain simulations in the benchmark proposed by the Spanish TSO.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the fundamentals of the control strategies considered for the GFM controllers. Section III outlines the methodology presented by the Spanish TSO for the evaluation of electromechanical oscillations when RESs are integrated into the power system. Section IV presents the simulation results for the three types of GFM controllers, which are compared to the base case (BC), i.e. the scenario in which RESs are not included. Finally, the paper closes with the main conclusions and future works.

II. GFM CONTROL MODES

This section describes the fundamentals of the GFM controllers used for the evaluation of the electromechanical oscillations.

A. S-VSG grid-forming controller

The control strategy of the S-VSG comprising an outer control loop (OCL) and inner control loop (ICL) is illustrated in Fig. 1. The former includes an active power loop (APCL) and a reactive power loop (RPCL), which are responsible for synchronisation and voltage adaptation with the grid. The APCL emulates the swing equation of a synchronous generator, where J and D are the rotational inertia and the damping coefficient, respectively. This control loop provides the angular frequency ω_{vsg} and the angle θ_{vsg} of the virtual rotor. The RPCL is based on a PI controller of the injected reactive power at the point of interconnection (POI), and provides the virtual electromotive force E of the synchronous generator emulated. The ICL is based on a classical PI current controller in the frame dq . The current references to the PI current controller are calculated using the virtual electromotive force E computed in the RPCL and a dynamic virtual impedance implemented through a low-pass (LPF) filter [16].

Of particular interest is the determination of the parameters J and D in the APCL, since they are responsible for providing inertia and damping. These are obtained following the approach presented in [17]. This takes into account the equivalent reactance of the network X_l and the virtual reactance X_v of the GFM controller to model the external grid in Laplace domain as follows:

$$G_g(s) = \frac{\Delta p(s)}{\Delta \omega(s)} = \frac{K_g}{s} = \frac{\omega_0 K_s}{s} = \frac{\omega_0}{X_t s} = \frac{\omega_0}{(X_l + X_v)s}, \quad (1)$$

where $G_g(s)$ represents the transfer function of the grid with output the active power increase $\Delta p(s)$ and input the frequency increase $\Delta \omega(s)$, ω_0 is the system nominal angular frequency in p.u., K_s is the synchronizing power coefficient in p.u., and X_t is total reactance.

On the other hand, the APCL of the S-VSG can be represented by the following transfer function:

$$G_{S-VSG}(s) = \frac{\Delta \omega(s)}{\Delta p^*(s)} = \frac{1}{\omega_0} \frac{1}{Js + D}, \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta p^*(s) = p^* - p$, is the active power error. This equation represents the APCL dynamics in units of the international system. Its equivalent in p.u. can be represented as follows:

$$G_{S-VSG}^{pu}(s) = \frac{\Delta \omega(s)}{\Delta p^*(s)} = \frac{1}{2Hs + D_{pu}} \quad (3)$$

where H is the inertia constant and D_{pu} represents the damping coefficient in p.u. When studying electromechanical oscillations, the dynamics of the ICL can be neglected, as they are much faster than those of the OCL. Therefore, the closed-loop transfer function of the APCL and the grid is:

$$G_{S-VSG}^{CL}(s) = \frac{K_g/2H}{s^2 + D_{pu}/2Hs + K_g/2H}, \quad (4)$$

which represents a second-order system, and its denominator polynomial can be associated with the damping δ and natural frequency ω_n as follows:

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{K_g}{2H}} = \sqrt{\frac{\omega_0}{2H(X_l + X_v)}}; \quad \delta = \frac{D_{pu}}{4\omega_n H}. \quad (5)$$

For a given value of the inertia constant H in the S-VSG, the natural frequency of the system ω_n can be obtained as a function of the reactances X_l and X_v , while the damping δ is set as a function of the value of D_{pu} . Note that the larger X_l and X_v , the lower ω_n and the greater the damping δ .

B. PI-VSG grid-forming controller

The distinction between PI-VSG and S-VSG is limited to APCL as shown in Fig. 1. In the case of the PI-VSG, this control loop is based on a PI controller applied to the POI active power error. The proportional and integral gains of the APCL, k_{pp} and k_{ip} respectively, provide the damping and inertial response of the VSG. In particular, the integral gain is associated with the inertia constant H as follows: $k_{ip} = 1/(2H)$, and k_{pp} is related to the VSG damping [15].

Despite being the only difference between both GFM implementations, the performance of both GFM controllers are considerable. The PI-VSG permits the damping response to be independent of the PFR, whereas this is not possible in the S-VSG due to the inherent provision of PFR by the damping factor D .

Similarly to the S-VSG, the APCL transfer function in the PI-VSG can be obtained as:

$$G_{PI-VSG}^{pu}(s) = \frac{\Delta \omega(s)}{\Delta p^*(s)} = \frac{k_{pp}s + k_{ip}}{s}, \quad (6)$$

with the following expression for the closed-loop transfer function:

$$G_{PI-VSG}^{CL}(s) = \frac{k_{pp}s + k_{ip}}{s^2 + k_{pp}K_g s + k_{ip}K_g}. \quad (7)$$

If the denominator of (7) is identified with the desired second order polynomial, the natural frequency and damping of the system are:

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{K_g}{2H}} = \sqrt{\frac{\omega_b}{2H(X_l + X_v)}}; \quad \delta = \frac{k_{pp}\omega_b}{2\omega_n H(X_l + X_v)}. \quad (8)$$

Fig. 1. Block diagrams of the grid-forming S-VSG and PI-VSG with the detailed controller of the OCL and ICL.

Note that ω_n is identical for the S-VSG and PI-VSG, and the damping δ is proportional to k_{pp} . However, unlike the S-VSG, the higher the reactances X_l and X_v , the lower the damping.

The last control strategy considered in the CIG is to integrate in the PI-VSG the ability to provide PFR including a classical droop control implemented by the proportional gain K_f as observed in Fig. 1 when the switch PFR is closed in the APCL.

III. POWER OSCILLATION REQUIREMENTS IN THE SPANISH GRID CODE

This section presents the requirements imposed by the Spanish TSO on RES-based plants to comply with the grid code (NTS) regarding inter-area power oscillations [13].

A. Benchmark for Evaluating Power Oscillations

The benchmark proposed by the Spanish TSO to evaluate the damping of power oscillations is shown in Fig. 2. The BC corresponds to the case where RES is not connected to bus 2. The system consists of two synchronous generators, one connected to bus 1, $G1$, and the other connected to bus 4, $G4$. Both generators are coupled to the grid by means of coupling transformers and are interconnected by a transmission line. The value of the transmission line reactance X_l is varied between 0.01 p.u. and 0.6 p.u. (base power 100 MVA) to evaluate different type of power oscillations. The base power of the generators, their controllers, the power generated by them and the consumption demanded by the loads are fully described in [13]. When the RES is integrated into the bus 2, this must satisfy a number of requirements in terms of power oscillation damping.

B. Requirements of Power Oscillations in RES

The NTS requires RES installations to dampen power oscillations in the 0.1-1.5 Hz range using a control system. If no such system is available, the RES installation must ensure that it does not negatively impact damping within this range.

The study of power oscillations can be conducted through the utilisation of either small signal analysis or time-domain

Fig. 2. The single-phase equivalent circuit proposed by the NTS as a benchmark for the evaluation of electromechanical oscillations.

Fig. 3. Graphical acceptance criterion for power oscillation damping using time simulations according to the NTS.

simulations. In the event that the study is conducted using small signal analysis, it is imperative to ensure that the damping of all oscillation modes exceeds 5%. Conversely, if the study is conducted using time-domain simulations, the power oscillation analysis is carried out graphically. This is achieved by subjecting the generator $G4$ in the benchmark proposed by the Spanish TSO to a variation of 2% of its reference voltage V_{ref} . In response to this disturbance, the power of the generator $G1$ is monitored with and without the presence of the RES, and the following study is performed (for illustrative purposes, please refer to Fig. 3).

- All maxima ($P1$ to $P5$) and all minima ($M1$ to $M6$) are

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE APCL IN THE GFM CONTROLLERS.

GFM VSG	H s	D_{pu} p.u	k_{ip} Hz	k_{pp}	p.u K_f p.u
S-VSG	5	11.21	0.1	---	---
PI-VSG	5	---	---	0.0054	---
PFR+PI-VSG	5	---	0.1	0.0054	20.0

connected by dashed lines.

- The first maximum ($P1$) is rejected if the first oscillation is rising or the first minimum ($M1$) if it is falling.
- The first cycle of oscillation between $M1$ and $M2$ is considered in Fig. 3.
- The magnitude $\Delta P1M1$ is measured in the manner indicated in Fig. 3: from point $P1$ a vertical line is drawn to its intersection with the line joining $M1$ and $M2$.
- The magnitude $\Delta P5M5$ is measured as shown in Fig. 3: a vertical line is drawn from point $P5$ to its intersection with the line joining $M5$ and $M6$.

The RES is considered to contribute adequately to the damping of inter-area oscillations if the following condition is satisfied:

$$\Delta P5M5 < 0,25 \cdot \Delta P1M1. \quad (9)$$

IV. CASE STUDIES

This section presents the findings of the evaluation of the damping of power oscillations in accordance with the NTS for four case studies: i) the BC, i.e. without RES, ii) the RES with S-VSG control mode, iii) the RES as PI-VSG control, and iv) the PI-VSG including the PFR: PFR+PI-VSG. The study of power oscillations is carried out using time-domain simulations and the value of the APCL controller gains for the GFM controllers are collected in Table I. These have been selected for providing a minimum damping δ of 5% in the worst case evaluated in the next subsection. The tuning of the rest of controller gains are computed following the methodology presented in [18].

A. Simulation Results

The power injected in bus 2 from the generator $G1$ under a voltage reference change V_{ref} in $G4$ from 1.0 pu to 0.98 pu for the line reactance interval, $X_l = [0.01 : 0.6]$, in the BC is illustrated in Fig. 4. It is evident that as the reactance value increases, the power oscillation concomitantly rises. However, it can be observed that the frequency oscillations fall in the range of 0.05-0.4 Hz, which corresponds to low-frequency electromechanical oscillations (inter-area oscillations). In any case, the results satisfy the requirement imposed by (9), which means that the power oscillations are properly damped in the BC for the entire range of X_l .

The impact of the RES integration with the considered controllers (S-VSG, PI-VSG, and PFR+PI-VSG) on the electromechanical oscillations is illustrated in Fig. 5. The left/right plots show a comparison of the four case studies for a low/high value of the line reactance, (0.1/0.6). Particularly,

Fig. 4. Power injected at bus 2 for several values of the line reactance $X_l = [0.01 : 0.6]$ in the BC.

the figure shows, from top to bottom, the power injected to bus 2 by $G1$, the RES power and the frequency of the center of inertia (COI) in the four cases in response to the change in the reference voltage V_{ref} .

For the low reactance value, it is observed that the incorporation of RES slightly reduces the oscillation frequency of the active power injected by $G1$ with respect to the BC. Despite this modification, the frequency remains at an approximate value of 0.0466 Hz, corresponding to inter-area oscillations. Furthermore, it is observed that this frequency is similar irrespective of the implemented GFM control. Regarding the overshoot, it is reduced with respect to the BC for all GFM approaches. Conversely, the damping is worsened in comparison to the BC for the PI-VSG. However, S-VSG and PFR + PI-VSG result in an improvement in comparison to BC. In any case, the three GFM approaches satisfy (9) ensuring adequate damping. The central plot displays the RES power during the disturbance. An initial reduction in active power due to the inertial response resulting from the frequency increase, as illustrated in the bottom plot, is showed in each RES. Note that the power variation of the S-VSG is greater than that of the PI-VSG due to the fact of its inherent PFR. This is also appreciated when included the PFR functionality to the PI-VSG. The advantages of GFM controllers are also evident if the frequency evolution is analysed. The rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) and the nadir are diminished in comparison to the BC, thanks to the RES active power reduction which serves to mitigate frequency fluctuations during the disturbance.

RES performance with high reactance is analogous to that observed in the analysis conducted with low reactance. However, in the presence of high reactances, the emergence of at least one new oscillation frequency superimposed on that of the BC is also observed. This issue is clearly manifests in the power delivered by the RESs in the middle plots. As a result, the use of the graphical method proposed by NTS for the analysis of electromechanical oscillation damping is subject to interpretation. This is because the selection of the maxima and minima value must be made in order to analyse the damping at a specific oscillation frequency. In the case of

RES integration, the choice of this frequency is not sufficiently clear, as can be seen from the injected powers in the top and middle plots. Similarly to the low reactance value, a reduction in the amplitude of the oscillations for the GFM modes are observed. Once more, the S-VSG and PRF+PI-SVG are the strategies that improve damping in comparison to the BC. With regard to frequency, it is evident that the GFM modes improve the RoCoF and the nadir, with this improvement being particularly pronounced in the S-VSG and PRF+PI-SVG.

Fig. 5. The left and right plots, from top to bottom, illustrate the following magnitudes with a reactance value of $X_l = 0.1$ and $X_l = 0.6$, respectively, in the four case studies: Power injected from G_1 to bus 2, Power injected from RES to bus 2, and COI frequency.

V. CONCLUSION

This work has assessed preliminary the influence of GFM VSCs on electromechanical oscillations in accordance with the benchmark established by the Spanish TSO. Simulations conducted in the time domain have demonstrated that GFM mode possess the capability to enhance the damping of these oscillations across the full range of line reactances evaluated. This improvement is more pronounced in the S-VSG than in the PI-VSG, due to the inherent damping and PFR characteristics of this type of GFM. It is only possible for PI-VSG to achieve comparable outcomes if the PFR service is incorporated into its control strategy. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that both the RoCoF and nadir are diminished in these operational modes. In addition, the results have demonstrated the emergence of novel oscillation modes when GFM controllers are integrated. In view of the findings presented in this study, a small-signal analysis is recommended as a future investigative avenue to ascertain the existing oscillation modes and their damping characteristics. This analysis can also calculate participation factors for each mode, helping to adjust GFM control parameters to improve

damping of electromechanical power oscillations. Finally, this approach can assess the necessity of integrating a POD when a GFM control strategy is unable to effectively damp these oscillations.

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